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Weed meal from a rice plot for broiler chicks

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Weeding contributes to the high cost of rice production in southern Nigeria. Many farmers cut and then burn weeds to control them. The biochemistry, economics of weed processing, and supplemental use of weed meal from rice (WMR) as broiler feed were evaluated as an integral part of the farming system.

A total of 354 kg of weeds were gathered from the farm plot, chopped, dried under shade 10–13 d before being exposed to slight sunlight on the 14th day, and then milled into ground particles with green coloration. Woody stems were removed before and during drying. The nutrient composition of both fresh and processed weed (weed meal) was determined following methods recommended by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC 1984). The weed population consisted of 71% grasses, 23% sedges, and 6% broadleaf weeds. Dominant weeds were *Echinochloa colona*, *E. crus-galli*, *Commelina benghalensis*, *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, and *Eclipta prostrata*.

Feed combinations for straight-run broiler chicks were (a) pure commercial feed mash (CFM), (b) CFM + 5% WMR, (c) CFM + 10% WMR, and (d) CFM + 15% WMR. One hundred and sixty commercial straight-run broiler chicks composed of 10 per plot (four replications) were fed for 8 wk. Response criteria (weight, feed consumption, mortality, breast-fleshing ability, feathering rate, pigmentation of skin and shanks, and incidence of cannibalism) were recorded and statistically analyzed using a complete randomized design.

The nutrient composition data indicated that weeds were rich in protein, ash, carbohydrate, fat, calcium, and phosphorus when processed into meal (Table 1). A total of 118 kg of fresh weeds was processed in this study. The cost of

the finished product was ₦1.39 kg⁻¹, which included costs of 0.94 ₦ kg⁻¹ for fresh weeds, 0.3 ₦ kg⁻¹ for drying, and 0.15 ₦ kg⁻¹ for milling (US\$1 = ₦85).

In all measures, the CFM + 5% WMR diet performed as well as the CFM diet (Table 2). The two diets with higher levels of WMR did not perform as well, as indicated by lower values of final weight, feed conversion efficiency, and breast-fleshing

ability. No effect of WMR on mortality was noted, even at the 15% level in the diet. All birds in the lots were fully feathered at 8 wk and their pigmentation was generally the same light yellow.

Reference

AOAC (Association of Official Analytical Chemists). 1984. Official methods of analysis. 14th ed. Washington, D.C.

Table 1. Nutrient composition of fresh and processed weed from rice farm plot.

Item	Nutrient composition (mg 100 g ⁻¹)	
	Fresh	Processed
<i>Proximate composition (N = 3)^a</i>		
Moisture	75.78 ± 0.14 b ^b	12.33 ± 0.07 a
Dry matter	24.22 ± 3.42 a	87.67 ± 0.95 b
Ash	2.26 ± 0.05 a	9.00 ± 0.34 b
Crude protein	2.15 ± 0.21 a	10.59 ± 0.94 b
Crude fat	0.68 ± 0.02 a	1.53 ± 0.22 b
Crude fiber	8.96 ± 0.11 a	34.49 ± 0.43 b
Nitrogen-free extract	10.17 ± 0.32 a	32.06 ± 1.03 b
Caloric value (kcal 100 g ⁻¹)	91.24 a	322.33 b
<i>Mineral content (N = 3)^a</i>		
Calcium	0.24 ± 0.04 a	0.92 ± 0.07 b
Phosphorus	0.10 ± 0.01 a	0.40 ± 0.04 b

^aValues are means ± standard deviations of triplicate determinations. ^bMeans in the same row with different letters differ at the 1% level of significance.

Table 2. Average production performance of straight-run broiler chicks.^a

Item	CFM ^b	CFM + 5% WMR ^c	CFM + 10% WMR	CFM + 15% WMR
Initial weight (g)	48.95	48.95	48.95	48.95
Final weight (g)	1,417.30 a	1,454.30 a	1,303.00 b	1,280.30 b
Total weight gain (g)	1,368.35 a	1,405.35 a	1,254.05 b	1,231.35 b
Daily weight gain (g)	24.43 a	25.10 a	22.39 b	21.99 b
Total feed consumption (g) ^d	3,509.80	3,618.50	3,662.20	3,563.60
Feed conversion efficiency	2.5 a	2.5 a	2.8 b	2.8 b
Broiler chicks at start of trial (no.)	40	40	40	40
Mortality (no.)	1	0	0	1
Breast-fleshing ability (%)	67.2 a	69.6 a	49.8 b	48.6 b

^aMeans in the same row with different letters differ at the 5% significance level. ^bCFM = commercial feed mash. ^cWMR = weed meal from rice. ^dAnalysis of variance showed no significance at the 5% level.